

Not Merely a Newsworthy Commodity: Jean-Paul Sartre's Engagement in the Struggle Against Apartheid

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ABSTRACT

Jean-Paul Sartre's renown and intellectual celebrity grew as a function of his engagement in Third World struggles. Sartre's public image as champion of the oppressed is so entrenched that it might seem self-evident that he played a leading role in the anti-apartheid struggle. However, his actual contribution to the South African struggle appears to be at odds with the way it is inscribed in collective memory. This article examines the incongruity between Sartre's actual involvement in the struggle against apartheid and his enduring image as a champion of the anti-racist struggle in South Africa. Archival research into Sartre's publications, public appearances and travels in France and abroad, note only three occasions on which Sartre made a direct reference to apartheid – the first in June 1963, the second in October 1964, and the third in November 1966. Tracing Sartre's involvement chronologically, the paper seeks to map more precisely the nature of Sartre's contribution, commitment and responsibility to the French anti-apartheid movement, to uncover different facets of Sartre as a celebrity and a public intellectual, and to offer a better understanding of the period following the Algerian War in France with regard to Third World struggles.

Keywords: Jean-Paul Sartre; public intellectual; Cold War; Third World struggles; Anti-apartheid Movement; social movements; Radical Left; *Christianisme social*

INTRODUCTION

The philosophy of Jean-Paul Sartre had a substantial influence on emancipatory discourses produced in the context of Third World struggles (Kalter 2016). The case of South Africa is no exception. Sartre's writings are indispensable when considering the role of the philosopher (Aronson 1990), and more generally, the responsibility of the intellectual towards society under apartheid rule (Sanders 2002). Furthermore, Sartre's writings were a source of inspiration for South African thinkers and activists such as Steve Biko, Noel Chabani Manganyi and Richard Turner (More 2008, Keninston 2013). Yet, while Sartre's writings and philosophy indirectly shaped the struggle against apartheid, his direct engagement with the anti-apartheid movement has rarely been explored. This relative lacuna has generated various misconceptions. Thus, it is commonly acknowledged that Sartre was deeply engaged in the French anti-apartheid movement during the 1960s. Wikipedia – a data-base whose influence on collective memory and social discourse cannot be overemphasized – names Sartre as the chair of the anti-apartheid committee, together with its actual co-founders, Jean-Jacques de Felice and Elizabeth Mathiot.¹ In a quite different institutional setting in October 1984, Joseph Nanven Garba, the Nigerian ambassador to the UN and the president of the UN's Special Committee against Apartheid, stressed the symbolic debt that that anti-apartheid movement owed to the famous French public intellectual:

There was a time in the 1960s and 1970s when we were obliged to express our disappointment and distress at the policy of the Government of France on apartheid [...] But we maintained faith in France. Our faith was sustained by the friendship and support of a number of French organizations and of eminent Frenchmen and women. I might make special mention of the great writer and philosopher, Jean-Paul Sartre, who inaugurated the French Anti-Apartheid Committee in the 1960s (Garba 1984).

Given the correlation between Sartre's worldwide renown and his engagement in Third World struggles (Kalter 2016), his public image as champion of the oppressed is so entrenched that it might seem self-evident that he played a leading role in the anti-apartheid struggle. Yet the archival record suggests that Sartre's celebrity as a public intellectual augments the memory of his contribution beyond its actual proportions, on the one hand, while this self-same celebrity was strategically instrumentalized by the

activists more centrally involved in the French struggle, on the other. Sartre's actual contribution appears to be at odds with the way it is inscribed in collective memory. In fact, the celebrated intellectual was never actually involved in the organization and management of the anti-apartheid movement. Michel Contat and Michel Rybalka (1974), who have compiled a list of Sartre's publications and public appearances in France and abroad, note only three occasions on which Sartre made a direct reference to apartheid – the first in June 1963, the second in October 1964, and the third in November 1966. In the discussion that follows, this incongruity will be examined in order to expose previously neglected aspects of the nature of intellectual celebrity and of the anti-apartheid struggle in France following the Algerian War of Independence.

This examination draws on Patrick Baert's "positioning theory" to account for the rise of Sartre to stardom in the immediate post-war years (Baert 2015, 2018). Baert's model shifts attention away from the intentions and motives which underly the interventions of intellectuals in politics and public affairs, focusing instead on the effect that these interventions produced on the public whom they addressed. The intellectual's intervention is thus regarded as a communicative interaction that the author/orator establishes with his public. Each such intervention, whether in a book, an article or a speech, entails a process of positioning by which the authors or the orators "allocate specific features to themselves and to others, thereby locating themselves within the intellectual arena or within the broader sociological or artistic context in which they operate" (2018, 231). In his case study, Baert demonstrates how "Sartre's rhetorical devices and his positioning in the specific political context in which he found himself, enabled the diffusion of his ideas within the public intellectual arena, helping to propel him to prominence" (2018, 231).

Baert's approach takes into account the agency of the public intellectual as well as the social and historical context of its production. Being a public intellectual is a social status, constituted discursively by the way in which the author/orator presents himself in the public sphere. Baert's notion of public intervention as a "discursive effect" also implies the presence of other actors in the cultural field – actors who bestow upon the intellectual celebrity the authority needed in order to become and to remain famous. Drawing on Amossy, we might observe that the practice of argumentation is used by

the public intellectual as an instrument to maintain or develop his image as a public intellectual and to position himself in the cultural sphere accordingly (Amossy 2006).

The media play a crucial role here, and are never merely a platform. Rather, the media actively participate in the construction of the intellectual's image through the way in which they choose to mediate this image to the public. The first occasion on which Sartre involves himself in a collective action against apartheid is a revealing example not only of the role of the media in the making of a celebrity, but also of the complex disposition of mutual relations and interdependence between different social actors involved in the celebrity making/maintaining of the public intellectual. A closer look into the content of Sartre's second and third texts on apartheid, along with the circumstances of their enunciation and publication, reveals how the historical *context* of the Cold War as well as the intellectual and ideological paradigm of Third-Worldism are a constitutive part of the *text* (Maingueneau 1996) and of the image of its author (Amossy 2010). Drawing on these analytical approaches offers a fresh perspective on Sartre's commitment to the institutionalization of the French anti-apartheid movement led by Jean-Jacques de Felice and Elizabeth Mathiot in the framework of the *Comité français de liaison contre l'apartheid*.

JUNE 24, 1963 – THE POST-ALGERIAN WAR AND THE INITIATION OF AN ANTI-APARTHEID MOVEMENT

The media played a crucial role in Sartre's rise to stardom (Baert 2018). The creation of the "Sartre phenomenon" (Galster 2001) during the 1940s stemmed from incessant press coverage and sensationalist headlines, greatly enhancing Sartre's visibility in the public sphere. The media shaped his social image in the process of transmitting it to the public. We can duplicate evidence of similar processes, in slow motion as it were, in the context of Sartre's first public intervention with respect to apartheid. On June 24, 1963, a press conference was organized in Paris to announce the founding of an anti-apartheid committee.² The organizers assembled a number of renowned intellectuals (Louis Aragon, Simone de Beauvoir, Jean-Marie Domenach, Pierre Stibb and others), former activists in the Algerian War, to sign a petition in favor of the ANC struggle in South-Africa.³ This petition was then addressed to the South African embassy in Paris. The involvement in the anti-apartheid initiative of members of the "Committee Maurice Audin"⁴ including Pierre Vidal-Naquet, Jacques Panijel, Paul Tibaut (of the journal

Vérité-Liberté) not only points to the important role that social movements played during the Algerian War, but also to the continuing commitment of their members to oppressed people in other Third-World struggles upon its conclusion.⁵ Sartre's celebrity status is reflected and confirmed through the coverage of the press conference in *Le Monde* the following day (25 June 1963), to my knowledge, the only record left of this press conference.

Although the conference was organized and supported by a group of public figures, the report presented Sartre's intervention in a way that overshadowed the collective dimension of this political action. This is evident from the title of the article "M. Jean-Paul Sartre announces the creation of an anti-apartheid committee" as well as from the formulation of the item:

Mr. Jean-Paul Sartre announced Monday morning, during a press conference, the creation in France of an anti-apartheid committee with a view to helping the Africans nationalists of South Africa. He specified that the committee would do all that it could to influence the public opinion as well as the French government and would endeavor to prevent it from sending weapons to the white government in SA.⁶

The importance that the article attributes to Sartre seems to surpass that given to the formal initiation of the struggle against apartheid in France. Sartre is the subject of the opening phrase. The temporal and spatial *deixis* ("Monday morning", "during a press conference") situate the speaker in the time and place of the enunciation, before the text orients the reader to the message about the anti-apartheid committee. The authority of Sartre confers on the struggle a sense of importance and urgency. The journalist is more concerned with the position held by the French intellectual on apartheid than with the words of Raymond Kunene, an ANC member exiled in London and an eye-witness to apartheid, which are relegated to the second half of the item. In other words, what is at stake here is the performance of the public intellectual rather than the struggle in which he engages. Furthermore, the article might give the mistaken impression that it was Sartre who launched the committee or took part in its ongoing management, while in fact he merely supplied symbolic support through participating in the event. It is thus the celebrity of Jean-Paul Sartre which lends the item its newsworthiness. Sartre's

endorsement of this cause – drawing primarily on his fame and, consequently, on his social power – may be indicative of a certain type of commitment expected of the public intellectual: a commitment which relies on one’s symbolic capital rather than on one’s actual participation in the ongoing management of an activist movement.

OCTOBER 24, 1964 – APARTHEID AS AN ARGUMENTATIVE CONSTRUCT IN SARTRE’S REFUSAL TO ACCEPT THE NOBEL PRIZE

In the above-mentioned case, Sartre’s authority stands adjacent to that of the pro-Algerian activists with whom the intervention began. But what happens when Sartre stands alone in the public arena weaving through his speech clear knowledge of his own singularity as an extraordinary emblem of politicized intellectual engagement? Sartre’s positioning with respect to his acceptance or rejection of the Nobel Prize, the next instance that we shall track, allows us to investigate a slightly different facet of his engagement with the South African struggle. In 1964, Sartre discovered in an article published in *Le Figaro littéraire* (October 15, 1964), that the Nobel committee was about to award him the Nobel Prize. He immediately wrote to inform the Prize committee of his irreversible decision not to accept it as well as to ask them to revoke their choice without making it public. Yet the letter did not arrive at its destination and the announcement of the new laureate went public. Sartre felt obliged to list the reasons for his rejection of the prize, which he did *in extenso* in an article published in the journals *Le Monde* and *Le Figaro* ten days later. The article provides fertile ground for an investigation of how Sartre’s positioning with regards to South Africa shifts in accordance with the ongoing prominence of the anti-apartheid struggle during the period immediately after the Rivonia Trial.

The article is divided into four parts. In the first part, Sartre expressed his apologies to the Swedish Academy. In the second, he explained his “personal reasons” for declining the prize, focusing principally on his need for autonomy, a precondition for him to carry out his intellectual engagements. Based on his “conception of the role of the writer,” Sartre argues that the writer must “refuse to let himself be transformed into an institution, even if this occurs under the most honorable circumstances, as in the present case.” By freeing himself of any kind of institutional constraints, the writer maintains his liberty to express, for example, his “sympathies for the resistance in Venezuela” without dragging “the whole institution of the Nobel Prize in it with him.”⁷

The Nobel Prize, however, did not ban the engagement of laureates in any kind of social struggles. On the contrary, it recognized and encouraged the social engagement of the writer as expressed in their publications and public activities. The Swedish Academy mentioned specifically that the Nobel Prize in Literature had been granted “to the French writer Jean-Paul Sartre for his work which, rich in ideas and filled with the spirit of freedom and the quest for truth, has exerted a far-reaching influence in our age.”⁸ The Nobel Prize Committee indeed prioritized the ideological aspects of Sartre’s work, referring implicitly to its social grounding and contribution to the class struggle in France and people’s liberation beyond France’s border (“rich in ideas and filled with the spirit of freedom [...] a far-reaching influence in our age”), rather than relating solely to the quality of his literary writings.

Yet, in his letter, the intended laureate does not address the reasons for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize. Sartre’s assessments rely on a higher objective, enfolded in the perception of the intellectual which he seeks to embrace and develop. From this perspective, the concept of autonomy is both a necessity for the intellectual to fulfill his intellectual engagements, and a constitutive element of his public image. Indeed, the refusal of the Nobel Prize reflects the Sartrian model of the intellectual whose power and privileges enable him to say “no!” and to counter the historical domination of the bourgeoisie (Bourdieu 1980). Paradoxically enough, the reasons put forward by the Nobel Prize committee for choosing the laureate, are also the reasons for which Sartre declines his nomination, since for Sartre the legitimacy of the intellectual to cultivate the spirit of freedom is conditioned by his own complete detachment from any institutional framework.

Sartre divides his arguments into personal and objective reasons for declining the prize, but in fact, the “objective reasons” which he presents in the second part of the article provide support for and justify the “personal reasons” presented in the first part. The theme of personal autonomy is thus subjugated to the political and historical context of the Cold War. According to Sartre, the Nobel Prize is an institution associated with and rooted in European culture and, therefore, reflects power relations between the Western block and the Eastern Block. Accepting the prize, in Sartre’s opinion, might be interpreted as a form of identification with one culture at the expense of the other.

Declining the prize would thus enable him “to work with everyone who wants to bring the two cultures together.” Sartre holds firmly to his autonomy and reaffirms, at the same time, his intellectual affiliation with the Third World, embracing its politics of nonalignment. The reference that Sartre makes to apartheid in South Africa, in the last part of his letter, is in line with the stand he takes on Third-Worldism in the preceding section:

Finally, I come to the question of the money. By adding a great sum of money to the honor, the academy places a very heavy burden on the laureate’s shoulders, and I have been tormented by this problem. On the one hand, one can accept the prize and with the money he receives support organizations or movements he thinks are important. I have been thinking of the anti-apartheid committee in London. On the other hand, one can decline the prize as a matter of principal, thus depriving this movement of the support it could have used.

Sartre’s refusal to accept the prize did not mean that he had not won it, however. Once the Prize Committee chooses a laureate, it cannot change its decision. “A double score for Jean-Paul Sartre”, declares the journal *L’Aurore*. (October 23, 1964) “He gets the Nobel, he refuses to accept it.” Even though Sartre did not receive the Nobel Prize, he did receive it on a symbolic level, just as he symbolically “donated” the prize to the anti-apartheid movement in London: for Sartre, as we know, the intellectual’s engagement in a social cause relies, first and foremost, on the “written word” rather than on material gestures.⁹ In this sense, by evoking the struggle led in London against apartheid, Sartre draws public attention to the situation in South Africa. Sartre’s statement in *Le Monde*, with its widespread diffusion in France and worldwide, helped strengthen both the anti-apartheid cause and his own moral and intellectual authority.

Most certainly, Sartre’s decision to focus upon apartheid in his speculations concerning the prize money derives from the urgency need, as he saw it, to put an end to an unjust regime and to protect the rights of black South Africans. But it also allows him to better perform his social role as a public intellectual, engaged on all fronts, as distant as those fronts may be. Distant, but not too distant. According to Anne Cohen-Solal (1987, 448), Robert Gallimard heard Sartre speak about another possible cause: the resistance of the Tupamaros in Paraguay during the 1960s. The archives of *Le Monde* show that public

opinion in France was completely unaware of this Third World struggle. From January first, until the end of December 1964, not a single article was dedicated to the struggle of the Tupamoras in Paraguay, while at least 20 articles make explicit reference to the Rivonia Trial and 20 others include the word “apartheid” in their title. *Le Monde* followed the developments of the Rivonia Trial closely (*Le Monde*, June 12), informed its readers of the protests in France and worldwide, and criticized the decision of the French government to abstain from any UN initiative calling for dismantling apartheid in South Africa (*Le Monde*, June 20). Both public opinion and the intellectual milieu were fully aware of the problem of apartheid in South Africa. On March 20, 1964, the UN published a declaration signed by 143 eminent personalities – including Simone de Beauvoir, Louis Aragon, Nathalie Sarraute, the English actor Sir Tyrone Guthrie, Sir Julian Huxley, Prince Souvanna Phouma, and the Dalai-lama – that condemned the Rivonia Trial (*Le Monde*, Mars 21). Later that year, a petition with more than 91,000 signatures, from 28 different countries, was handed to the UN to try to save the lives of the Rivonia accused (*Le Monde*, June 17).

Obviously, Sartre did not calculate the frequency of the references to “apartheid” in *Le Monde* before entering in communication with his public. Nevertheless, his prioritizing of the struggle against apartheid over that of the Tupamoras in Paraguay is not incidental. Sartre was well acquainted with the interests and inclinations of the French public to which he belongs and to whom he addresses his text. By taking the audience into account, Sartre, like any other orator, seeks to increase the acceptance of the theses presented for the assent of that audience (Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca 1971). Press interest and the consequent growing public concern with the military and economical collaborations between France and Pretoria (Van Vuuren 2017), and more largely, the *doxa* of the epoch in regards to the controversial issue of apartheid in the immediate aftermath of the Rivonia Trial, thus played a constructive role in Sartre’s line of argumentation and contributed to the global reputation that he was in the process of constructing for himself by rejecting the Nobel Prize.

NOVEMBER 9, 1966 – SARTRE AND *LE COMITÉ FRANÇAIS DE LIAISON CONTRE L’APARTHEID*

While Sartre tried to avoid all forms of institutional dependency, his legitimacy nevertheless relied heavily on institutional forces that gave the public intellectual a

platform on which to perform his social role. The third occasion on which Sartre addresses the subject of apartheid took place on November 9, 1966, at a press conference held by the *Comité français de liaison contre l'apartheid* led by Jean-Jacques de Felice and Elisabeth Mathiot.¹⁰ Before examining the dynamic that arose between Sartre and the *Comité*, the formation of the movement needs to be considered. The establishment of the *Comité* was first and foremost dependent on the work done by de Felice and Mathiot within the institutional framework of the protestant movement *Christianisme social*. Embracing Third Worldist viewpoints, this ecumenical movement tried to combine Christian theology of liberation with Marxist theory of revolution (Crespin 1993, Terretta 2015), encouraging its Protestant members to collaborate with Marxist activists against the exploitation of the Third World, by European capitalism.¹¹ The review *Christianisme social*, named after the movement, was a think tank in which the interest in apartheid could be consolidated and converted into direct action led by people from within the movement, supported by others.¹²

The *Comité* came into prominence together with the reorganization of *Christianisme social* after the Algerian War and scaled down its activities with the gradual dissolution of this social movement at the end of the 1960s. In the French context, the end of the Algerian War was a decisive moment. The outcome of the war produced an effect of demobilization in most of the social movements. The period of “hesitation and confusion” (Crespin 1993) that followed the Evian Accords in March 1962 presented an opportunity to conduct organizational changes and to set new goals. Yet, it was primarily the struggle against the war in Vietnam that captured public attention in France following the end of the struggle for the Algerian independence. The fight against apartheid, a regime which the French government was partly responsible for maintaining (Konieczna 2012, Van Vuuren 2017), captured far less public attention. In retrospect, the influence of the *Comité* was limited to the second half of the 1960s. By 1970, *Christianisme social* temporarily ceased to operate and so, too, did the *Comité* (Crespin 1993).

The press conference convened by the *Comité* on November 9, 1966, with Sartre at its head, had as its primary goal the announcement of an international colloquium on the apartheid regime that was due to take place in Paris the following year. The timing of the announcement reflected developments in South Africa in the months leading up to

it. Earlier that year, the *Comité* had busied itself with a social campaign against the arrest of Bram Fischer, Nelson Mandela's lawyer at the Rivonia trial, a battle to which de Felice was personally committed being a lawyer himself. The condition of the political prisoners, dissidents of the regime in power, had a powerful impact on French intellectuals, engaged, until recently, in the Algerian liberation struggle.¹³ As we have already noted, the collective memory of the Algerian War was used to generate identification with the anti-apartheid struggle and to stimulate collective action against it.

However, the organization of the press conference was equally bound up with sociological considerations regarding the institutionalization of a social movement and its positioning in the intellectual arena. The epistolary exchanges between members of the executive bureau of the *Comité* and other personalities reveal the major role which the *Comité* hoped that Sartre would play. The news of Sartre's participation in the conference opens the letter that de Felice wrote to Mathiot on the April 7, 1966 (Fonds Jean-Jacques de Felice 1966a): "[T]he news is reassuring: Sartre has given his agreement for a large-scale juridical meeting under his presidency. He will discuss it with Senghor (...)." Mathiot's reply came the following week, on April 11, 1966: "I am thrilled by the participants that you announced ... They will contribute to making the *Comité* known and to valuing its work as essential in the current political context" (Fonds Jean-Jacques de Felice 1966a).

The large number of invitations sent out before the conference attests to the efforts made by de Felice and Mathiot to reach social movements and activists from all spheres of the intellectual field in France and abroad – journalists, writers, scholars and philosophers, former militants in the Algerian War, lawyers and jurists, members of *Christianism social* as well as other progressive movements,¹⁴ ANC members and other South-African dissidents in exile (Raymond Kunene, Robert Resha, Breyten Breytenbach, Albie Sachs, Leslie Rubin and others), anti-apartheid activists from Europe and the Guinean Achkar Marof, the head of the UN Special Committee Against Apartheid at the time. The various collaborations initiated by the *Comité* are a good indication of its intentions to produce a decisive impact on public opinion in France concerning the political reality in South Africa (Terretta 2015).

And yet, the influence of Jean-Paul Sartre on the public sphere seems to eclipse that of any other intellectual of his time. A close look at some of the invitations reveals the discursive and argumentative effect produced by the reference “Jean-Paul Sartre”. Pierre Mendes France, former Prime Minister (1955), was asked (October 16, 1966) to “assist (...) the press conference that we organize with J.-P. Sartre” (Fonds Jean-Jacques de Felice 1966b). Canon Collins was informed (October 10, 1966) that the *Comité* would execute the decision taken during the July’s meeting to organize the “conference for November 9, with Jean-Paul Sartre.” Raymond Kunene, an ANC member exiled in London, was also asked (October 19, 1966) to take part in “the important press conference with Jean-Paul Sartre” (Fonds Jean-Jacques de Felice 1966d). De Felice (October 11, 1966) attaches great importance to the presence of the Pastor Charles Westphal, the president of the Protestant Federation of France, in the “extremely important press conference as it will gather around Monsieur Jean-Paul Sartre and Monsieur Daniel Mayer, the most qualified representatives of French organizations” (Fonds Jean-Jacques de Felice 1966d). A letter was also sent (October 11, 1966) to Pierre Bungener, a Protestant pastor and a leading figure in the Anti-apartheid Committee in Geneva. De Felice (Fonds Jean-Jacques de Felice 1966d) explicitly links the battle over public opinion and the press conference led by Sartre:

We are entering a difficult period in the struggle against apartheid in the public opinion. We are carefully preparing the press conference of November 9 around Jean-Paul Sartre and Daniel Mayer, to announce a big international meeting scheduled for next spring in Paris.

The references to Sartre indicate the extent to which his name carries authority. The invocation of his presence not only validates the importance of the conference but also implies that the act of participating in it is also valuable: each of the addressees was invited to deduce that “if Sartre is there, I must be there too.”

A short review of some of the newspapers that covered the conference demonstrates that the *Comité* was not alone in stressing the importance of Sartre’s contribution. In the headline of *France-Soir* “Sartre: ‘France is wrong in initiating relations with South Africa’”¹⁵ (November 11, 1966), and in *Le Monde* from the same day, “An international conference on the ‘apartheid’ will be held next year in Paris, announces M. Jean-Paul

Sartre”, the journalists predicate the validity of the message on the authority derived from the identity of its enunciator, Jean-Paul Sartre. In the title “Sartre and apartheid”, published in *Nouvel Observateur* (16-22 November, 1966), the focus shifts entirely away from the conference to Sartre. Even the media in South Africa expressed interest in his opinion, as is evident in the title of an item published in the evening newspaper *The Star* (November 12, 1966) on the press conference held in Paris: “Sartre wants action on S.A”. In all these headlines, Sartre is the subject, the focal point through which the information concerning apartheid is transferred to the reader. Once more, the journalists seem more interested in Sartre’s opinion about apartheid than in apartheid itself.

“A CANCER IN AFRICA”: ON SARTRE’S SPEECH AT THE PRESS CONFERENCE

Sartre’s speech at the press conference was published in its entirety in the press under two titles, both expressive of the responsibility that a committed public intellectual might seek to assume in the social sphere. The first, by *Christianisme social*, published in the November-December 1966 edition, read: “A cancer in Africa. Racist propaganda in support of apartheid.” The second, published in December by *Droit et liberté*, the journal of the MRAP, stated: “Those who are confronting apartheid should know that they are not alone.” Each title projects a different image of the intellectual: The first depicts Sartre as a social analyst and as a severe critic of the injustice of apartheid. The second reflects an image of Sartre as the protector of the “wretched of the earth.” Yet the text of Sartre’s address is equally revealing. He begins with a bold assertion: “Today there is in Africa a cancer that could quickly spread all over. It is Apartheid, a policy systematically practiced by the Government of South Africa.”¹⁶ Sartre establishes an analogy between the political regime of apartheid and the fearsome and fatal disease of cancer. This emotive analogy attracts public attention to the orator as well as implying that apartheid might potentially endanger French society. Finally, the cancer metaphor constitutes a call for action to which the audience is invited to respond. The appeal to fear is evoked once more in the concluding lines of the talk:

If we don’t succeed in mobilizing the majority to the struggle in a profound and serious manner, we will be responsible and complicit through our

passivity for a virulent and intolerable neo-Nazism which will emerge from South-Africa and spread its infection all the way to Europe.

The medical language (“infect”) gives the passage the appearance of a quasi-medical diagnosis that transforms the society into a living body and the speaker-observer into an analyst announcing its decline. The use of the linguistic markers of future time (“will immerge from South-Africa and spread its infection”) and of the conditional tense (“If we don’t... we will be responsible and complicit”) creates the impression of a prophet announcing the end of society; the conditional tense is constitutive of an affirmative and categorical tone that implies that the alternative offered by Sartre is the only option. The reference to Nazism implies a comparison between the racial atrocities of the World War and the ones committed by the apartheid regime. It reinforces the effect of fear by emphasizing the immediate danger that apartheid represents to the French people while activating their collective memory of the dark years under the Nazi occupation. Finally, the historical reference to Nazism plays a substantial role in discursive intensification. This analogy was in fact already in use, in a similar manner, during the last years of the Algerian war as a response to the violent escalation of the war (Kalter 2016, 123). The emancipatory discourse produced by Sartre in regards to apartheid relies on one already in place concerning the urgent demand to decolonize Algeria.

Prophetic rage is well expressed in the accusation formulated by Sartre against the French government that had proclaimed, six years earlier, “its solidarity with the countries of the third world, with the newly independent nations”, and which now chooses to become complicit in “acts of terror and slaughter to which colonizers are subjecting colonized people at the tip of Africa and preventing them from achieving independence”. The words “terror”, “slaughter” and “independence” enable Sartre to stage a dramatic triangle that links the “executers” (colonizers from Europe) and their “victims” (colonized of the Third World), while assuming for himself the prophetic role of the “savior”. This scenography strengthens the authority of the engaged intellectual, allowing him to establish the ethical and moral standards which underlie the plan of action now announced: “to affirm solidarity with the resistance movements – not only verbal solidarity, but practical and effective solidarity.”

The engagement of the public intellectual is also performed in the core of the text where an analysis of apartheid is offered. The first part of the presentation discusses apartheid as a practice. The second part elaborates the racist theory on which the practice of apartheid is based. Sartre mediates apartheid to the public. He demonstrates his own mastery of the facts while implying his audience's ignorance. By doing so, Sartre reconstructs and reinforces, in discourse, his social power and authority. If the conference is thrust into the limelight by virtue of Sartre's participation, Sartre in turn enjoys increased attention by being afforded a stage on which to construct himself as a prominent public intellectual.

It is important to note that the discrepancy between the image of the engaged intellectual as reflected in Sartre's speech and his own evaluation of the importance of his participation in the conference. Sartre seemed to have had other obligations that prompted him to leave before the press conference ended. Leslie Rubin wrote to Sartre and expressed his deep regret at his early departure (November 10, 1966). Rubin and Canon Collins also exchanged impressions about the press conference that they both found disappointing. A few months after the conference, on March 13, 1967, Collins summed up the conference as follows¹⁷:

I find myself in great difficulty in regard to the French situation. International Defense and Aid has spent quite a lot of money over the Sartre venture; (...) I cannot really feel that any great good has come out from our visit to Paris except perhaps the name of Sartre on the paper.

Collins minimized the impact of the conference. He did not miss the fact that the public was more interested in Sartre than in his subject. According to Denis Herbstein, Canon Collins was deeply offended by the interaction between Sartre and his followers which he saw as based on blind admiration and loyal support. "When he [Sartre] sat down most of the audience left. They had only come to hear a famous Frenchman", says Herbstein, noting this as the reason why Canon Collins "never wanted to go back to France again" (2004, 229).

As for Jean-Paul Sartre, the sense of wariness felt by the British associates in regards to his commitment to the anti-apartheid struggle turned out to be justified. The

intellectual celebrity ultimately failed to participate in the colloquium that he himself had announced a year earlier. In the abundant choice of Third World struggles, Sartre took a stand with the popular public opinion against the war in Vietnam. Sartre joined the famous Russell Tribunal in Stockholm, from where he sent a message of regret to the organizers of the conference, ensuring them that if the “tribunal had taken place in Paris, [he] would have done what was necessary to be present at least in the opening session” (Fonds Jean-Jacques de Felice 1966e). It seems, in the final analysis, that the engaged intellectual who wishes to lead public opinion, is no less led by it.

CONCLUSION

This article has sought to provide a better understanding of the disparity between Sartre’s actual implication in the struggle against apartheid and his enduring image as its champion. Tracing Sartre’s involvement chronologically, this incongruity may be at least partly explained by locating the contribution of the (public) intellectual celebrity to the French anti-apartheid movement within the historical context following the Algerian War in France, with regard to the intellectual and ideological paradigm of Third-World struggles.

The journalistic coverage of the activities led by the anti-apartheid movement shows the extent to which Sartre’s engagement went far beyond questions of ethics or morality. His celebrity as a public intellectual was needed to focus attention on the question of apartheid beyond the circles of the intellectual elite and to publicize the systematic oppression of blacks in South Africa as well as the support extended to the apartheid regime by the French government. The social functions fulfilled by Jean-Paul Sartre shed light on his positioning in the cultural field as an influential personality. The perception of apartheid in French society, an issue of secondary importance to Sartre, provided an opportune moment to put into practice his theory of engagement. The social position of the intellectual celebrity laid the groundwork for a specific mode of engagement. Sartre, though seemingly committed to the struggle against apartheid, showed little interest in the institutional work involved in this struggle. It is clear that Sartre’s social position enhanced the visibility of the *Comité* in the public sphere, and amplified the reach of its message. In return, Sartre maintained his own visibility thanks to the platform that the *Comité* offered him. Sartre committed his symbolic capital, his fame and prestige, to the struggle against apartheid and in the process revalidated his

status as an “icon of cultural engagement” (Dine 1998). It is perhaps a reflection on the working of celebrity itself that Sartre has become inscribed in collective memory for his role in the French anti-apartheid movement.

Sartre’s engagement in the struggle against apartheid has the power to illuminate the history of Third World Struggles conducted by a radical left in the aftermath of the Algerian War. The Algerian War played a determining role in shaping Third World movements and the discourse they promoted. This historical (1960s), political (post Algerian War) and institutional (*Christianisme social*) history is inscribed in the workings of the *Comité*, and more specifically, in the organization of the Press conference of Sartre, undertaken toward the end of 1966. The struggle against apartheid that Jean-Jacques de Felice and Elisabeth Mathiot took upon themselves revealed the inter-relations between social progressive movements in France and between intellectuals more generally. Sartre’s various interventions in this regard shed light not only on the strong ties that connected different domains within the intellectual fields (political, juristic, journalist, academic, literary, etc.) but also on the importance that eminent intellectuals accorded to the problem of apartheid. This despite the fact that it was not considered the most urgent cause facing French society. Finally, the use of the public image of Jean-Paul Sartre, the worldwide famous intellectual, by the French anti-apartheid movement, may also reveal how the engagement of Sartre in the struggle against apartheid validated and reinforced his social status as a public intellectual and celebrity, inscribing him, for posterity, as a champion of this struggle.

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¹ https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Opposition_internationale_%C3%A0_l%27apartheid (accessed September 20, 2019). See also the African Activist Archive on the *Comité français contre l'apartheid*. <http://africanactivist.msu.edu/organization.php?name=Comit%C3%A9%20fran%C3%A7ais%20contre%20l%27apartheid> (accessed September 20, 2019)

² The committee was composed as followed: President – Laurent Schwartz; Secretary – Pierre Vidal-Naquet, Serge Thion; Treasury – Henri Stern; Bureau – Manuel Bridier (PSU/Cedetim), Claude Lanzmann (*Temps modernes*), Louis Martin-Chauffier (sociwriter/socialist), Ernest Milcent, Jacques Panijel, Paul Thibaud, the last two founded the journal *Vérité-Liberté*, a strong voice of opposition against the War in Algeria. I would like to express my gratitude to Anna Konieczna for providing me this information. For further details, see her article (2017), exploring the activity of the first anti-apartheid movements in France during the 1960s.

³ In a similar way to the Manifesto of 121, published in in the journal *Verité-liberté*, which was an open letter signed by 121 French intellectuals supporting the Algerian's struggle for independence, and denouncing the use of torture by the French army (Andersson 2012).

⁴ [The Committee was c](#)reated during the Algerian War in order to find out the causes of the death in jail of Maurice Audin, assistant professor at the University of Alger, arrested alive by the French troops on June 11, 1957.

⁵ In 1964, the Anti-apartheid committee published *Les Brutes* – a French translation of a report circulated by the ANC on the conditions of political prisoners in South Africa, based on their own accounts smuggled out of the Pretoria prison. The text was printed in France with the support of the members of the Maurice Audin Committee. The comparison between the methods of oppression in use during the Algerian War and the ones in practice by the apartheid regime is presented to the reader on the back cover of the book. Drawing on French collective memory, the reference to the Algerian War created a sense of identification with the problem of apartheid and, consequently, raised awareness of it within French society.

⁶ All translations are mine, unless otherwise indicated.

⁷ Sartre's letter was translated to English by Richard Howard and published under the title "Sartre on the Nobel Prize" in the *New York Review of Books*, December 17, 1964.

⁸ "Announcement. Address by Anders Österling, Member of the Swedish Academy." NobelPrize.org. Nobel Media AB 2018. <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/literature/1964/press-release/> (accessed October 19, 2018)

⁹ For Sartre, "a writer who takes a position on political, social, or literary questions should rely only on the means which are his – the written word" (*Le Monde* 1964).

¹⁰ The term "press conference" is, in fact, a little misleading as the public event attached to it was far broader. Under the umbrella of the press conference, Canon John Collins, the British founder of International Defense and Aid Fund for Southern Africa (IDAF), and Leslie Rubin, South African jurist in exile and a staunch opponent of apartheid would take the stage alongside Jean-Paul Sartre. This would be followed by a round table hosting eminent personalities such as André Philip, lawyer, politician and regular contributor to the review *Christianisme social*, and Daniel Mayer, president of the LDH (Human Rights League).

¹¹ See for example the article "Notre message Chrétien social" ("Our Christian social message") published in *Christianisme social* by Léonard Ragaz in the immediate post-war period (January-February 1948).

¹² In 1960, de Felice joined the Human right league ("Ligue des droits de l'Homme") and contributed his first article in the review *Christianisme social* to the violation of human rights during the Algerian war. From this point on, de Felice published regularly on various social and political issues, with the purpose to unmask the close relations between the State law and social injustice. Elisabeth Mathiot, the secretary of the Comité, had already contributed to the review *Christianisme social* on gender issues and women rights.

¹³ During the 1950s de Felice defended juvenile delinquents from the poor neighborhoods of Nanterre (Seine, Hauts-de-Seine), and became, later on, a lawyer of some prominent FLN leaders. Elisabeth Mathiot and her husband, the protestant pastor Etienne Mathiot, were active in the FLN resistance movement in France. When Etienne Mathiot was prosecuted for assisting an FLN militant in 1958, *Christianisme Social* stood by his side – a special issue of the review was dedicated to the case.

¹⁴ Such as the MRAP – Movement Against Racism and for Friendship between Peoples; LICRA – International League against Racism and Anti-Semitism; LDH – The Human Rights League; UNEF – The National Union of Students of France.

¹⁵ "Sartre: La France a tort de commencer avec l'Afrique du Sud ».

¹⁶ I quote from the English translation available on *A history of Apartheid in South Africa*. <https://www.sahistory.org.za/archive/those-who-are-confronting-apartheid-should-know-they-are-not-alone-jean-paul-sartre>. Accessed on June 2, 2018.

¹⁷ I thank Anna Konieczna for sharing this information with me.